

TRAINING THE YOUNG ATHLETE: THE ESSENTIAL ROLE OF BOXING AS A DISCIPLINE

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Abstract

This research work analyzes young people's training process in boxing, understood as a discipline that gives rules through a specific training practice. Training thus becomes a psycho-physical well-being path, in which the sacrifices due to the discipline, imposed by the rules, can be worthwhile for the rest of life, both as a permanent cultural practice and to promote the comparison between diversity and socialization. This construction path, through the culture of work, will see young people as representatives of the positive values of sport, especially against marginalization and school dropout, thus enhancing the values of an ancient sport like boxing.

Keywords: Formative process; Sport; Boxing; Talent; Youth training and regulation.

Introduction

The discipline of boxing is based on individual values and on the conditional and coordination skills, as well as on courage, tactical intelligence, strength, speed and dexterity. The key to success to enhance the young talents of this sport is the implementation of a methodological model, aimed at building the skills of young promises. All professionals in the field must work to ensure that this training process can be carried out by means of a project with a training methodology that starts with the organic development of the youngest age groups. In fact, the development of skills necessary for the success of the future boxer must start from the foundation. Therefore, the training methodology will have to consider the stages of psycho-physical, social and cognitive development as a fundamental prerequisite to structure the growth project plan, hinged on the axes of pedagogical orientation and teaching practices, and based mainly on the synergistic action with families and schools. Consequently, it follows that the lifelong, technical-specific training of professionals is essential just like the training methodology, the work plans and the choice of means.

at this direction, and that the sports associations of cities or suburbs follow the same direction too, since they are well aware that the standardization of the sports talent of boxing leads to the risk of discarding other talents, because too premature or too far from being close to the Champion standard. For this reason, the formative process relying on a training programming guarantees different perspectives. In fact, it cannot overlook cultural indicators

that take into account the athletes' different languages and values, and how sensitive they are to issues related to culture and gender. Instead, other cross-cutting goals of the boxer's training must aim at tolerance, social cohesion and responsiveness to the needs of young athletes with disabilities or behavioral/learning problems. In light of this, the skills of a good technician or boxing master must be structured according to the rapid progress of areas of knowledge and methodological expertise, discipline-specific teaching practice, pedagogical orientation, communication and relationship, organizational skills, and finally, methods of evaluation of different youth groups. Therefore, it follows that the success of the training process depends on the degree of preparation of the experts in the field, especially the instructors, trainers, doctors, technicians, masters and managers. They all must be able to prepare the young promises of boxing to civil coexistence, respect for the rules and a self-directed approach to learning, and they must be able and motivated to keep expanding their knowledge throughout their life. Thus, the perspectives of the aforementioned operators should be: facilitation, knowledge, learning design, pedagogy, evaluation, reflection, and finally, collaboration and development. Consequently, the specific skills of the technical masters must include the ability of self-evaluation, based on a training methodology which focuses on knowledge and empathic skills, collaboration, acceptance of daily difficulties, foresight, interest, tenacity, flexibility, responsibility, reflection, admission of one's own mistakes and patience, so that the daily educational practice is based on the organization and motivation of all athletes of the various youth groups. So the real difficulty will be in the management of the progression of learning and in the consequences of differentiation by test matches, tournaments or championships won by individual young boxers. Boxing is a sport in which the competition is single, but the choices of who has to fight are made within a team. Many athletes train, but only one competes in national, European or world competitions. Since the victory then belongs to a single athlete, the personalization/individualization and involvement of everyone in the task is very complex. For this reason, using a project based on the many criteria described above, supplemented by the use of technology especially for functional evaluations, can make it possible to face the duties and dilemmas of the profession with fewer mistakes, and can also better support the choices to be made, based on the continuity of the search for and development of talents. This requires lifelong learning and professional management, enriched by skills upgrading, useful for the enhancement of human and social capital, by systematically reflecting on practice and learning again from experience while keeping up with the evolution of educational theories and research. Hence, it is correct that technical rationality is given its rightful place through an epistemology of practice and action. A fusion, therefore, of academic knowledge and skills based on experiences in the gym, at the side or at the corner of the ring. A combination of mental reasoning and action, as Dewey taught us. But the result of all this favors both the construction of the reputation of the single gyms, to which the young talented boxers belong, and the whole national boxing movement. In fact, the training tasks also hold responsibilities in a national and world key. The

talent development encompasses all the training agencies, starting first of all from the family, and then involving the amateur sports associations and the boxing federation, up to CONI (Italian National Olympic Committee). The discovery of a talent, his or her overall development and sports and social integration will be the right award, and will have the right professional and social acknowledgement. Thus, it is not about the "isolated talent", but the structure that contributes significantly to the "common challenge of boxing". Mere reputation is not enough; it must be spent on the professional community, the boxing movement, and the entire national sport.

2. Regulations of the Italian Youth Boxing

The activity of the youth sector of the Italian Boxing Federation is expressed in the general document approved by the Federal Council dated December 07, 2015, with Resolution No. 483, and reviewed again by the Federal Council dated April 13, 2019. It prescribes the contents and methods of the recreational-sports training. This regulation seeks to build an educational path in which sports practice becomes: a psycho-physical well-being path to be taken during our existence as a permanent cultural practice; a moment of sports comparison to evaluate ourselves; an instrument of attraction for young people, so that they can express themselves, accept diversity, and therefore socialize; an instrument for spreading the positive values of sport, which turns young people from users into bearers of the values themselves; a tool to fight school dropout and marginalization. If what described above represents the criteria for recreational sport activities (boys and girls from 5 to 13 years old), something different is the world of competitive activities (boys and girls from 14 to 18 years old and divided by weight category), regulated in AOB (Aiba Open Boxing) tournaments. It is the acronym in which the International Boxing Association (AIBA) encloses all those tournaments once considered for "Amateurs", both at national and international level; young AOB boxers participate in public competitions for pure agonistic spirit and not for profit, available to the Italian Boxing Federation and its Bodies for the preparation and the execution of competitions of federal interest at regional, interregional, national and international level, in Italy and abroad.

3. Training Theories and Practices

A first important consideration concerns the use of both theoretical and practical innovations in relation to the formative process of technical, tactical, physical and psychological training in the youth boxing sector. The new theories of the training methodology include new training means, now defined as functional and subject to the physical law of change, thus conditioning the high demand for specialization, which is now widespread even among the groups of athletes in the growth phase. Other factors predisposed to transformation and promoters of innovative contamination are also the continuous need for attention to nutrition and for new technological systems, especially in relation to functional assessment. The second factor, however, is related to the increase in specialized training, in the general volume of technical and physical preparation. This phenomenon reduces working times, directing training towards different directions, especially towards future specializations, and thus

slowing down the development of the natural aptitudes of young boxers. The strong individualization accelerates the emphasis of work plans according to the competitive structure, leaving less and less room for recreational activities through which it is possible to learn by trial and error, and where the exploration of the solution guides young people towards the discovery of their motor skills. The latter will be better structured, with the advantage of being more long-lasting and comprising the basic motor schemes, the true growth and development platform for coordination and conditional skills. Even the introduction of new technologies, if not used for the mere purpose of measuring or for functional evaluation, can lead to a strong emphasis on natural skills, increasingly individualizing the programming of training in relation to the competitive structure characterized by the speed of movements in changing conditions, strength endurance and speed. In an attempt to rebalance the training loads and volumes in relation to matches and competitions, recovery and nutrition are often modified, stimulating and conditioning the work capacity and the mobilization of functional resources. This leads to an excessive focus on immediate success. Instead, the development of talent involves physical, technical, mental and cognitive training, set over years of work and through a general defined training, especially in contemporary society that has almost eliminated public games played in the streets and parks from social behavior. In the light of what pointed out, the search for immediate high-level performance will not allow to spread the adaptations on an extensive overall volume, predisposed to wait for the acquisition of subsequent specialized and targeted experiences; so the required adaptations will not find a morpho functional base already complete and developed, but a substrate of temporary skills and abilities, generated by the auxological, and therefore precarious development of the moment.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the training process represents a value not to be wasted, because it favors a methodology which learning turns out to be organized in a project with the perspective of re-evaluating collective professional identities, pushed to trace the aspects of cooperation and joint effort in the daily training practice carried out in the gyms they belong to, also in favor of a national central mechanism. For this reason, the leadership of sport, among the various proposals offered both by the new functional methodologies and technological innovations and by the increasingly specialized and individualized training means, must succeed in safeguarding the training of talent from the invasion of the complexity of innovations. This is necessary to enhance the operational resources of those working in the field based on creativity, and without the rush of immediate success, thus making good use of time in favor of the laws of natural, gradual and indirect physical development.

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